

Rethinking Climate Strategy in Nigeria: How Policy and Regulation will Enable Nigeria's Journey Net Zero and Economic Growth

PRECIOUS C.D OPARANOZIE

1. Introduction

In Nigeria, climate change attributable to human activities¹ is not merely a scientific theory to be debated, but a harsh reality that threatens the lives and livelihoods of millions of citizens and the socio-economic wellbeing of the country. In October 2022 alone, climate change induced-floodings resulted in the deaths of over 600 people and left about 1.5 million women, men, and children displaced, majority of whom also lost farmlands.² Coastal regions are severely plagued by erosions that have exacerbated landslides and swallowed whole villages, such as the Erstwhile village in Delta State.³ According to estimates by the World Bank, the continued rise in sea levels due to global warming could soon drown up to three-quarters of Niger Delta and parts of Lagos – Nigeria's economic heartbeat.⁴ In Northern regions, the increasing temperatures is accelerating desertification and heightening the possibility of severe droughts similar to recent occurrences in the horn of Africa.⁵ Holistically, climate change presents a grim picture, which could amplify existing challenges in the country: poverty, food insecurity, unemployment, and security; and could impede sustainable economic development.⁶

¹ According to the United Nations, "since the 1800s, human activities have been the main driver of climate change, primarily due to burning fossil fuels like coal, oil and gas."

<<https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/what-is-climate-change>>, accessed March 15, 2023.

² Please refer to this news report:

<<https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.voanews.com/amp/climate-change-fueled-rains-behind-deadly-nigeria-floods-study-finds-/6838154.html>>. According to this report, Researchers from the World Weather Attribution (WWA) consortium said in a study that the floods, among the deadliest on record in the region, were directly linked to human activity that is exacerbating climate change.

³ World Bank Group (2023). *Nigeria's Vulnerability to Climate Change*.

<<https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/nigeria/vulnerability>> accessed March 13, 2023.

⁴ World Bank Group, *ibid*.

⁵ Haider, Huma (2019). "Climate change in Nigeria: impacts and responses". IDS,

<<https://opendocs.ids.ac.uk/opendocs/handle/20.500.12413/14761>> accessed March 13, 2023; UN News, (2023). "Somalia: \$2.6 billion appeal to support millions amid historic drought and famine fears", <https://news.un.org/en/story/2023/02/1133272#> accessed March 15, 2023.

⁶ According to experts, climate change will cost Nigeria up to USD 460 billion by 2050 if strategic intervention is neglected (*Nigeria's National Adaptation Plan Framework, p.1*).

Recognising the need for high-level and systemic intervention to mitigate climate change whilst remaining responsive to the broader development needs of the country, the Nigerian government has developed key strategies for climate action in line with its international climate change pledge to become carbon neutral by 2060, embodied in a plethora of legislation, policies, and regulatory measures. This essay, therefore, seeks to examine how Nigeria's climate policies and regulations can pave the path to a prosperous future that integrates her commitment to achieve Net Zero by 2060.⁷ Following this introduction, a brief definition of terms would be provided; then, an overview of Nigeria's current climate action strategy would be succinctly examined. Thereafter, the pathways through which these policies and regulations can achieve sustainable economic growth and climate targets would be analysed. These issues would ultimately be synthesised in the conclusion and actionable steps for the way forward will be recommended.

2. Definition of Terminologies

2.1. Climate Change

Climate change refers to the "long-term alteration in global weather patterns, particularly in relation to temperature, precipitation, and atmospheric conditions." These changes are largely caused by human activities such as burning fossil fuels and deforestation, leading to increased greenhouse gas concentrations, ozone-layer depletion, and global warming.⁸

2.2. Net Zero

According to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, Net Zero refers to achieving a balance between the amount of greenhouse gas emissions produced and removed from the atmosphere; otherwise known as carbon neutrality. This can be achieved through reducing emissions, utilizing renewable energy sources, and carbon capture and storage. The ultimate goal is to limit global temperature rise to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels to avoid the worst impacts of climate change.⁹

2.3. Policy and Regulation

Policy and regulation refer to the laws, rules, and guidelines set by government bodies to deliver specific goals, such as improving public health, protecting the environment, or promoting economic growth.¹⁰

⁷ Energy Transition Plan Working Group (2022). *Nigeria's pathway to achieve carbon neutrality by 2060*. <<https://energytransition.gov.ng/>> accessed March 13, 2023.

⁸ Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (2021) "Climate Change: The Physical Science Basis" <<https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/>> accessed March 13, 2023.

⁹ United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. (2021). "Net Zero." <<https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/the-paris-agreement/net-zero>> accessed March 15, 2023; International Energy Agency. (2021). Net Zero by 2050: A Roadmap for the Global Energy Sector. <<https://www.iea.org/reports/net-zero-by-2050>> accessed March 15, 2023.

¹⁰ OECD (2023). "Regulatory Policy". <<https://www.oecd.org/gov/regulatory-policy/>> accessed March 15, 2023.

2.4. Sustainable Economic Development

In conventional economic thought, environmental sustainability was decoupled from economic growth and both were regarded as mutually exclusive. However, with new insights as to how environmental challenges like climate change can have severe negative impacts on economic growth and the opportunities in green economies, the narrative has changed.¹¹ Thus, *Britannica* defines sustainable economic development as "an approach to economic planning that attempts to foster economic growth while preserving the quality of the environment for future generations".¹²

3. A Critical Examination of Nigeria's Climate Action Strategy

Nigeria's Climate Action Strategy is enunciated in its policy and regulatory framework for climate change. At the level of international law, Nigeria is a party to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) of 1992, and is signatory to both the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement of 2015.¹³ In addition, the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and AU's Agenda 2063, which Nigeria is privy to, also prioritise accelerated socioeconomic development that mainstreams environmental sustainability.¹⁴ Nigeria also has a significant number of home-grown policy instruments that are unarguably comprehensive on climate change and sustainability. Some of the most recent of these are examined below:

3.1. Climate Change Act 2021

At COP26, Nigeria committed to attain carbon neutrality by 2060, and the following week President Muhammadu Buhari signed into law the Climate Change Act 2021.¹⁵ Nigeria's Climate Change Act outlines an ambitious plan to integrate climate action within national development priorities and establish the net-zero target for 2050-2070. The Act mandates the Ministry of Environment to set a carbon budget and limit emissions in line with UNFCCC's target to reduce global temperature levels.¹⁶ Also, it provides for the periodic formulation of a National Climate Change Action Plan to ensure consistency with carbon budget goals and identify climate adaptation and mitigation measures.¹⁷ Another remarkable provision is its directive for public and private entities to implement low-carbon emission mechanisms; and the obligation of private

¹¹ IISD (2023). "Sustainable Development".

<<https://www.iisd.org/mission-and-goals/sustainable-development>> accessed March 15, 2023.

¹² Britannica, (2023). "Sustainable Development"

<<https://www.britannica.com/topic/sustainable-development>> accessed March 15, 2023.

¹³ Ladan, Muhammed (2022). "Nigeria's Climate Change Act and Policy 2021 and the Future of Climate Litigation", <<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4019698>> accessed March 15, 2023.

¹⁴ UN Sustainable Development Goals, Goal 13 centres on Climate Action;< <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>> and African Union Agenda 2063 emphasises on sustainable economic prosperity;< <https://au.int/en/agenda2063/overview>>

¹⁵ PWC (2021). "Nigeria's Climate Change Act – things to know and prepare for".

<<https://www.pwc.com/ng/en/publications/nigeria-climate-change-act-things-to-know.html>> accessed March 13, 2023.

¹⁶ The target is to limit global temperature increase to within 2 degrees celsius, and pursue efforts to keep it within 1.5oC above pre-industrial levels.

¹⁷ Section 20, Climate Change Act 2021.

entities with 50+ employees to have an annual carbon emission reduction plan and a designated climate change officer.¹⁸ The Act further establishes the National Council on Climate Change, chaired by Nigeria's President, to coordinate national climate actions, administer the Climate Change Fund, and promote nature-based solutions.¹⁹

3.2. The National Policy on Climate Change 2021-2030

Initially initiated in 2013 and revised in 2021, the National Policy on Climate Change is a comprehensive strategy that aims to incubate low-carbon economic growth and build climate resilience.²⁰ It sets specific targets to establish national capacity for climate change adaptation, accelerate afforestation, and enhance energy efficiency, in line with objectives that encompasses strengthening national institutions and mechanisms for climate change governance and encouraging research, public awareness, and private sector partnerships.²¹ The policy sets these key targets: minimizing current energy consumption by half, ending gas flaring, and a 20% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2030.²²

3.3. The National Adaptation Plan (NAP) Framework 2020

The NAP framework harmonises Nigeria's past and current policy responses to climate change, particularly with regard to adaptation measures. It aims to articulate Nigeria's vision of climate change adaptation and align the NAP process with existing policies and strategies, to the end of enhancing Nigeria's adaptive capacity and reducing vulnerability to the impacts of climate change. The framework also seeks a multisectoral mainstreaming of climate change adaptation into relevant policies, programs, and activities across all levels of decision-making. It further lays down the approach and structure of the NAP implementation process, its institutional arrangements, guiding principles, monitoring and evaluation, and its funding strategies.²³

3.4. Nigeria's Energy Transition Plan 2022

The Energy Transition Plan (ETP) is Nigeria's latest autochthonous, data-supported, and comprehensive strategy to achieve net-zero emissions in the country's energy use by 2060.²⁴ The plan involves a multi-faceted approach to reducing emissions in five key sectors: Power, Cooking, Oil and Gas, Transport, and Industry. Also, it aims to meet the nation's energy

¹⁸ Sections 24; Climate Change Act 2021.

¹⁹ Section 15, Climate Change Act 2021.

²⁰ National Policy on Climate Change 2021-2030; Grantham Research Institute (2023). "National Policy on Climate Change and Climate Change Policy Response and Strategy". <https://climate-laws.org/geographies/nigeria/policies/national-policy-on-climate-change-and-climate-change-policy-response-and-strategy> accessed March 13, 2023

²¹ Ibid.

²² Ibid

²³ The National Adaptation Plan (NAP) Framework 2020; <https://napglobalnetwork.org/resource/nigeria-national-adaptation-plan-framework/> accessed March 13, 2023.

²⁴ Energy Transition Plan Working Group (2022). Nigeria's pathway to achieve carbon neutrality by 2060. <https://energytransition.gov.ng/> accessed March 13, 2023.

requirements while simultaneously achieving the 2060 net-zero target by transitioning to renewable energy solutions which maximise energy efficiency in order to minimise its consumption, thus "reducing emissions and powering development".²⁵ Among its chief objectives includes lifting 100 million Nigerians out of poverty, providing modern energy services to the entire population, and becoming a beacon for fair and inclusive energy transition in Africa.²⁶

3.5. Nigeria Economic Sustainability Plan 2020

Notably, the plan makes provision for climate action by aiming to (among others) create 250,000 job opportunities within renewable energy and supplying electricity to 5 million households by 2023. The plan also promotes private sector participation and provides a financial incentive for solar energy innovators to receive assistance in obtaining low-interest loans from development finance institutions and the CBN.²⁷

Other key policy instruments include the National Action Plan to Reduce Short-lived Climate Pollutants, National Action Plan on Gender and Climate Change for Nigeria, Medium Term National Development Plan 2021-2025, and The Flare Gas (Prevention of Waste and Pollution) Regulations 2018.

4. Pathways to Enable Sustainable Economic Growth and Climate Targets through Policy and Regulation

Policy and regulation, as a mechanism of governance, plays a major role in the sustainable development of any country, possessing the power to either hinder or accelerate growth. In terms of climate action, policy instruments also play an equally powerful part.²⁸ This section of the essay would elucidate on how Nigeria's current climate policies and regulations examined earlier, through ensuring compliance, encouraging green entrepreneurship, mobilising finance, mainstreaming adaptation, and education and awareness, would enable the country not only to meet its 2060 net-zero target, but also to achieve economic prosperity in the process.

4.1. Ensuring Compliance

Policy and regulatory instruments are necessary to ensure compliance by both public and private institutions to climate targets, which is why the enactment of the Climate Change Act in 2021 was historic as it established a solid legal framework for Nigeria's climate action strategy. Such legislative certainty has been noted to be central to creating institutional mechanisms, like the National Council on Climate Change, that can facilitate a synergised and efficient response

²⁵ Ibid

²⁶ Ibid

²⁷ Grantham Research Institute (2023). "Nigeria Economic Sustainability Plan". <https://climate-laws.org/geographies/nigeria/policies/nigeria-economic-sustainability-plan> accessed March 13, 2023.

²⁸ OECD (2023). "Climate Action: Explore policy solutions by key economic sectors". <https://www.oecd.org/stories/climate-action/key-sectors/> accessed March 15, 2023.

to climate action.²⁹ Furthermore, some legal experts have opined that the Act provides sound legal grounds for possible climate litigation where the obligations it imposes are breached. Incidentally, those provisions align with **Section 20 of Nigeria's 1999 Constitution (as amended)** that provides that "The State shall protect and improve the environment and safeguard the water, air and land, forest and wildlife of Nigeria".³⁰

Nigeria's current legal framework for climate action would strengthen the rights-based approach to environmental litigation adopted by the Supreme Court in **Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v. NNPC**³¹, where it held that a clean and healthy environment was a fundamental human right of every citizen, and thus the government agency was duty-bound to protect citizens from harmful activities of oil companies. Also, in **Jonah Gbemre v. Shell, NNPC and AGF**,³² the court held that oil companies must stop gas flaring in the plaintiff's region due to its impact on local communities **and** its contribution to negative climate changes. While these cases were primarily within environmental jurisprudence, they set a precedent for the future of climate action.

4.2. Encouraging Green Entrepreneurship

With Nigeria's green economy potential valued at \$250 billion,³³ there is a huge untapped opportunity for green entrepreneurship particularly in agriculture, waste management, and energy sectors that can create decent jobs, spur economic growth, and fast-track the country's journey to reach its climate targets. Green Entrepreneurship involves innovating viable, profitable, and sustainable solutions to tackle climate and environmental challenges available through climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies.³⁴ Evidence has shown that policy framework is vital to promoting green entrepreneurship in Nigeria, as it lays the foundation for promoting green technology, provides fiscal and monetary incentives to establish market and investment, and allows for capacity building.³⁵ For instance, provisions like the enhanced access

²⁹ Ladan, Muhammed (2022). "Nigeria's Climate Change Act and Policy 2021 and the Future of Climate Litigation", <<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4019698>> accessed March 15, 2023

³⁰ Section 20, Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. Although this provision expresses the state's fundamental objectives and principles of state policy, by virtue of **Section 6(6)(c)** of the Constitution, it is rendered non-justiciable.

³¹ (2019) 5 NWLR pt. 1666, p. 518

³² (2005) FHC/B/CS/53/05

³³ Okojie, J. (2019). "Nigeria's green economy can create \$250bn investment opportunity for entrepreneurs – Experts". (*Business Day*, September 2).

<<https://www.google.com/amp/s/businessday.ng/amp/interview/entrepreneur/article/nigerias-green-economy-can-create-250bn-investment-opportunity-for-entrepreneurs-experts/>> accessed March 15, 2023.

³⁴ Anabaraonye, J; Chukwuma, J, Edinburgh, C. (2019). "Green entrepreneurial opportunities in climate change adaptation and mitigation for sustainable development in Nigeria". *Journal of Environmental Pollution Management* 2 (2), 102.

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Benjamin-Anabaraonye-2/publication/332765995_Green_Entrepreneurial_Opportunities_in_Climate_Change_Adaptation_and_Mitigation_for_Sustainable_Development_in_Nigeria/links/5cc8811d92851c8d2210008d/Green-Entrepreneurial-Opportunities-in-Climate-Change-Adaptation-and-Mitigation-for-Sustainable-Development-in-Nigeria.pdf> accessed March 15, 2023.

³⁵ Enuoh, R.O; People, G.J.; Kekong, B.P. et al (2020). "Green Entrepreneurship and Business Performance in Nigeria". *Solid State Technology*, 63 (6), 15767.

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Grace-Pepple/publication/351905515_GREEN_ENTREPRENEURSHIP_AND_BUSINESS_PERFORMANCE_IN_NIGERIA_A_CONCEPTUAL_REVIEW/links/60af835f928>

to credit finance for solar innovators under Nigeria's Economic Sustainability Plan 2020 made the sector more attractive to entrepreneurs, which can be said to be among the reasons why the number of startups in the solar energy sector has grown sporadically over the past three years.³⁶

Net job creation per sector

Figure 1. Source: *Nigeria's Energy Transition Plan*. According to these estimates, Nigeria's net-zero pathway will result in up to 340k jobs created by 2030 and up to 840k jobs created by 2060 driven mainly by the Power, Cooking and Transport sectors.

4.3. Mobilising Finance

Policy is a strategic means to mobilise finance, which is very essential to achieve Nigeria's climate targets. According to the National Energy Transition Plan Working Group, the country

[51c168e447d8f/GREEN-ENTREPRENEURSHIP-AND-BUSINESS-PERFORMANCE-IN-NIGERIA-A-CONCEPTUAL-REVIEW.pdf](https://www.esi-africa.com/industry-sectors/generation/solar-energy-in-nigeria-has-powerful-impact-on-socio-economic-status/)> accessed March 15, 2023.

³⁶ Tena, N. (2022). "Solar energy in Nigeria has powerful impact on socio-economic status". (ESI Nigeria). <<https://www.esi-africa.com/industry-sectors/generation/solar-energy-in-nigeria-has-powerful-impact-on-socio-economic-status/>> accessed March 15, 2023.

needs \$1.9 Trillion to achieve Net Zero by 2060, including \$410 Billion above projected usual spending – ultimately translating to approximately \$10 billion annually.

Estimated Cost of Nigeria's Net Zero Target

Figure 2. Source: *Nigeria's Energy Transition Plan*.

Covering these huge costs would take coordinated efforts, clear pathways, strong institutions and established partnerships which can only be created by comprehensive policy and regulatory framework. Hence, financial and monetary policy instruments are influential in climate mitigation and adaptation efforts.³⁷ Within Nigeria's current climate strategy, the Climate Fund established under the Climate Change Act performs the function of funds' mobilisation as carbon taxes, grants, donations, and other funding from international organisations, fines and charges issued to private and public entities, among others; are forwarded to it.

4.4. Education and Awareness

³⁷ Oman, W. (2019). *A Role for Financial and Monetary Policies in Climate Change Mitigation*. (International Monetary Fund, September 22). <https://www.imf.org/en/Blogs/Articles/2019/09/04/a-role-for-financial-and-monetary-policies-in-climate-change-mitigation> accessed March 15, 2023

Mainstreaming climate change issues in education, as well as sensitisation of the public to the negative impacts of climate change and actions they ought to imbibe to mitigate and adapt to it, is integral to Nigeria's sustainable socio-economic development. That is because the eventual success of these reforms is largely dependent on the cooperation of non-state actors: particularly the ordinary citizens who wield significant power. Policy and regulation is necessary to achieve this. Thus, majority of the climate policies examined earlier include enlightenment and awareness campaigns.

5. Conclusion

Nigeria has developed policies and regulations to combat climate change and attain its net-zero target by 2060. The government is focusing on ensuring compliance, encouraging green entrepreneurship, mobilizing finance, mainstreaming adaptation, and promoting education and awareness. These strategies not only contribute to Nigeria's global climate commitments but also provide a pathway for sustainable economic growth. Integrating these policies and regulations can pave the way to a prosperous future while mitigating the impacts of climate change. It is vital that Nigeria continues to implement these measures and invest in renewable energy sources to achieve its net-zero target and create a greener and more sustainable future.